

Development And Evaluation of Herbal Mosquito Repellent Coil from *Azadirachta Indica* Flower Oil Using Natural Binders

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ABSTRACT

The present study was undertaken in order to develop and evaluate the mosquito repellent property of neem (*Azadirachta indica* Family-Meliaceae) flower oil based coil using some natural binders. Neem flower oil based coil were prepared using different natural binders such as neem powder, wood powder, coconut shell powder and cow dung. All flower base coils were impregnated with extracted neem flower oil of different concentrations i.e. 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% using methanol as a carrier alcohol. The evaluation of mosquito repellent activity was carried out based on three parameters as flammability, burning efficiency with respect to burning time and mosquito repellent activity of the coil. The results showed that neem flower oil coil with neem powder as a binder; impregnated with 15% neem flower oil has the most effective repellent activity. From the present study it can be concluded that neem flower oil coil can be used as potential repellent against mosquitoes.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*, Mosquito repellent, Neem flower oil, Natural binders, Meliaceae.

INTRODUCTION

Azadirachta indica (Neem), a tree originally from India and Myanmar called by many “The village pharmacy” or “Divine tree” because of its many health properties. In recent times, Neem-derived extracts have been shown to work from anywhere from insect repellent to supplements to lower inflammation, diabetic control and even to combat certain types of cancer.

Neem plant has its role as health-promoting effect is attributed because it is rich source of antioxidant. It has been widely used in Chinese, Ayurvedic and Unani medicines worldwide especially in Indian subcontinent in the treatment and prevention of various diseases. Earlier findings confirmed that neem and its constituents play a role in the scavenging of free radical generation and prevention of disease pathogenesis. The plant product or natural products show an important role in disease prevention and treatment through the enhancement of antioxidant

activity, inhibition of bacterial growth and modulation of genetic pathways. The therapeutic role of natural plants in disease management is still being enthusiastically researched due to their less side effect and affordable properties. It has been accepted that drugs based on allopathy are expensive and also exhibit toxic effect on normal tissues and on various biological activities. It is a largely accepted fact that numerous pharmacologically active drugs are derived from natural resources including medicinal plants [1, 2]. Mosquito control has become crucial in today's environment due to the increased incidence of mosquito-borne diseases such as dengue, chikungunya, malaria, yellow fever, encephalitis and many others [3, 4]. Mosquitoes are one of the most vexing bloodsucking insects that humans face which kills millions of people every year [5, 6]. In endemic areas, malaria, which is brought on by Plasmodium parasites and spread by female Anopheles mosquito bites, continues to pose a serious threat to newborns and young children. The *Aedes aegypti* mosquito is the cause of dengue disease, which infects about 100

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million people annually globally. Around the world, mosquito control is a major public health concern. One strategy for controlling these diseases spread by mosquitoes is to stop the spread of the disease by either eliminating the mosquitoes or stopping them from biting people. By taking a virus or parasite with them when they bite an infected person or animal, these mosquitoes typically spread diseases from one person to another or from one animal to another.

Mosquitoes are alone responsible for the transmission of diseases to approximately 700 million people worldwide, with more than one million deaths every year [7]. Therefore, mosquito control and protection against mosquito bites has become the most significant measures to combat such diseases.

The World Health Organization has advocated different initiatives to control mosquitoes like environmental management of mosquito breeding areas and use of chemical insecticides [8]. Other measures include repellents, netting, clothing and other personal protections [9]. Mosquito repellents are efficient in preventing mosquito bites since they may be used in any place and at any time [8] and can be applied to the skin or any other surfaces where mosquitoes normally settle [10]. Applying a material to skin, clothing, or other surfaces that prevents mosquitoes from landing or climbing on them is known as a mosquito repellent. Repellents for mosquitoes are used to shield the body from bites that may have systemic or localized consequences. Many chemical repellents are available in the market. These products often contain active ingredients such as DEET (N, N-diethyl-meta-toluamide), Picaridin, IR3535 or para-menthane-diol (PMD)^[19,20]. DEET (N-N-diethyl-m- toluamide) is a potent insect repellent available nowadays in variety of forms such as pump sprays, creams, sticks, impregnated towelettes in 5% to 100% concentrations etc [4, 9]. Similarly, mosquito coils consists of synthetic pyrethroids as active components which have significant effect on the mosquitoes but their odor are disliked by many individuals and are thought to cause health complications [3] and also acts as potent mutagen, carcinogen and teratogen [4, 11, 12]. Therefore, new active, particularly natural compounds have been

sought as an alternative for these synthetic chemical repellents.

Plants have been utilized for ages against mosquitoes and other vectors due to its repellent property against mosquitoes and other vectors by hanging bruised plants in houses, as crude fumigants and oil formulations. It is still widely practiced in many developing nations as well as in many traditional communities [13]. Therefore, plant based mosquito repellent have been identified as an alternative to synthetic repellents as they are effective, easily biodegradable, environment friendly, less costly and have no side effects [6]. Based on the present market scenario of mosquito repellents and based on ethnomedicinal claims the present study was aimed to develop and evaluate an herbal mosquito repellent coil with natural binders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Neem flowers: Fresh flowers of neem tree were collected from Ahilyanagar district of Maharashtra in March 2025 and authentication for plant material was carried out at department of botany Padmashri vikhe patil college Pravaranagar, Maharashtra.

Figure 1: Flowers of *Azadirachta indica* Plant

Extraction Of Essential Oil: The flower were subjected to steam distillation for extraction of oil. The extracted oil was then stored at a low temperature (4°C) until use. After the distillation process, the flower remains were collected for preparation of flower coil [3, 6, 14].

Preparation Of Flower Coil Using Natural Binders:

The petals were grounded into a paste using distilled water by a kitchen blender for preparation of coil. The coils were prepared using 20% (w/w) of each natural binder and 80% of the neem flower paste. 50 gm of the paste were placed in different disposal plates and mixed with 4 different natural binders. The natural binders used were neem powder, wood powder, coconut shell powder and cow dung. Therefore four different combinations of coil were obtained. The coils were prepared in duplicates for each combination and neem flower paste without binder was taken as a control. Wet weights of each cake were taken. The coils were then dried in the sun. After 4-5 days of drying the dry weight was taken [3]. Preparation of different combinations of coil is shown in Table 1.

Impregnation of the neem flower coil with oil: The coil were sprayed with the extracted essential oil of the neem flower of different concentrations, i.e. 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% using methanol as a carrier alcohol (Figure 2).

Collection of mosquitoes: The mosquitoes were collected using a net between 6 pm to 9 pm. The mosquitoes were then caged and provided with a 5% sugar solution until processing [15, 16].

Figure 2: Prepared mosquito repellent coil

Evaluation of mosquito repellent activity:

The evaluation of mosquito repellent activity of neem oil coil were carried out based on its flammability, burning efficiency with respect to burning time and mosquito repellent activity [3, 17, 18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The flammability, combustion time and effectiveness of the herbal repellent made up of different formulation of binders with neem flower remains were checked by burning the coil. The results of the present study showed a variable difference of the coil in their effectiveness towards mosquito. The amount of water loss was calculated by using the wet and dry weights of the coil. The average water loss was found to be 37.28 gm (Table 2).

Table 1. Table showing different combinations of coils prepared with their subsets

Composition of cake	Nomenclature	Subsets
Neem flower paste	Control	Control + 0% neem flower oil
		Control + 5% neem flower oil
		Control + 10% neem flower oil
		Control +15% neem flower oil
Neem flower paste + 20% wood powder	Preparation-I	Preparation-I + 0% neem flower oil
		Preparation-I + 5% neem flower oil
		Preparation-I + 10% neem flower oil
		Preparation-I + 15% neem flower oil
Neem flower paste +20% coconut shell powder	Preparation-II	Preparation-II + 0% neem flower oil
		Preparation-II + 5% neem flower oil
		Preparation-II + 10% neem flower oil
		Preparation-II + 15% neem flower oil
Neem flower paste+ 20% neem powder	Preparation-III	Preparation-III + 0% neem flower oil
		Preparation-III + 5% neem flower oil
		Preparation-III + 10% neem flower oil
		Preparation-III + 15% neem flower oil
Neem flower paste + 20%	Preparation-IV	Preparation-IV + 0% neem flower oil

cow dung	Preparation-IV + 5% neem flower oil
	Preparation-IV + 10% neem flower oil
	Preparation-IV + 15% neem flower oil

Table 2. Average wet and dry weights of neem flower oil coil.

Name of Samples	Average wet weight (gm)	Average dry weight (gm)	Water loss (gm)
Control	50±0	9.3±1.1	40.7
Preparation-I	50±0	14.2±1.1	35.8
Preparation-II	50±0	17.0±1.2	33.0
Preparation-III	50±0	12.9±1.4	37.1
Preparation-IV	50±0	10.2±1.2	39.8

Average water loss=37.28 gm

Flammability and burning time test:

15 gm of cake from each type of dried coil were burnt to maintain the uniformity to check the parameters. The residual percentage of the coil was calculated based on ash weight and dry weight of the coil (Table 3).

The lowest residual percentage was found to be of preparation-III impregnated with 15% neem flower oil and the highest was found to be in preparation-IV impregnated with 0% neem oil. The maximum time for combustion was found to be of the control coil whereas; the minimum time was taken by the coil under preparation-III.

The coils were also checked for their irritability factor. The control, preparation-I and preparation-II showed no irritability whereas; preparation-III showed little irritability and had a burning effect on eyes. Preparation-IV showed high irritability and also had a burning effect on eyes with a pungent smell. It was also observed that the coil of preparation-I, preparation-II and preparation-III were fully flammable but the coil under control and preparation-IV were partially flammable (Table 3).

Test For Effectiveness:

(a) In field test: The coil were burnt in mosquito prone areas of boys hostel PVP College, Pravaranagar, Ahilayanagar district of Maharashtra

state and the reviews of students were noted down. The reports were positive i.e. the mosquitoes escaped from the area of burning (Table 4).

The total combustion time and the time of repellence showed by each cake are shown in Table 5. Preparation-III showed the maximum repellence for at least 180 minutes, followed by Preparation-II. Control and Preparation-IV showed repellence for a total of 120 minutes approximately, while the least repellence was seen in Preparation-I.

(b) In-vitro test: The total number of mosquitoes killed with respect to total combustion period of the coil and specific time period of 15 minutes were evaluated by the smoke toxicity test shown in Table 6.

The results showed that, during a specific time period of 15 minutes, the highest number of mosquitoes killed was 14 in Preparation-III, while, the least number of mosquitoes killed was 5 in Preparation-I. On the basis of total burning time of the coil, the highest number of deaths recorded was 26, in Preparation-III, while, the least number of death was 13, in Preparation-I. It can also be inferred from the given data that the effectiveness of the coil increases with the increase in the concentration of neem oil impregnation.

Table 3: Different parameters for checking the burning time and flammability test

Samples	% of neem oil	Total dry weight (gm)	Ash content (gm)	Total burning time in minutes	Total Residual %	Irritation test	Flammability (PF – Partially flammable FF – Fully flammable)
Control	0	15	5.1	46	35	No	PF
	5	15	4.0	42	29	No	PF
	10	15	4.1	42	28	No	PF
	15	15	4.52	38	36	No	PF
Preparation- I	0	15	3.01	36	21.4	No	FF
	5	15	2.71	32	18.1	No	FF
	10	15	3.02	28	20	No	FF
	15	15	3.01	29	17.1	No	FF
Preparation-II	0	15	2.24	28	18.2	No	FF
	5	15	2.31	24	16.1	No	FF
	10	15	2.13	28	14.7	No	FF
	15	15	2.46	32	16.1	No	FF
Preparation-III	0	15	1.60	26	10.2	Little	FF
	5	15	1.09	24	10.6	Little	FF
	10	15	1.62	26	7.0	Little	FF
	15	15	1.32	21	7.3	Little	FF
Preparation-IV	0	15	7.21	30	32.4	High	PF
	5	15	6.98	32	38.2	High	PF
	10	15	5.20	28	37.0	High	PF
	15	15	5.25	34	34.8	High	PF
Synthetic repellent coil	--	15	5.20	35	33.8	High	FF

Table 4. Mosquito repellency test in different areas of College hostel campus.

Areas	Observations	Remarks
Hostel premises	Mosquitoes escaped	Good mosquitoes repellency seen
Laboratory	No mosquitoes were observed	Good mosquitoes repellency seen
Cafeteria	Mosquitoes escaped	Good mosquitoes repellency seen

Table 5. Comparison of time for effectiveness of the coil after burning of full cake

Neem cake Samples	Total Combustion time (min)	Effectiveness				
		30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	180 min
Control	61	+	+	+	-	-
Preparation-I	36	+	+	-	-	-
Preparation-II	32	+	+	+	+	-
Preparation-III	26	+	+	+	+	+
Preparation-IV	38	+	+	+	-	-
Synthetic repellent coil	51	+	+	+	+	+

The results of the comparison between the neem oil coil formulated with different herbal binders and a synthetic repellent showed that the synthetic repellents was more efficient than the neem oil coil with different herbal binders (Figure 3). The mosquito

repellent activity of the different types of plant extracts and essential oils is compared. They found that all the essential oil show more repellency than plant extracts [5]. A number of synthetic pesticides or repellents used to control insects pose various

environmental and human health risks [10] and are mostly expensive [21]. Therefore, natural products with high efficacy and low environmental impact are searched as an alternate approach and plants are considered as an effective alternative. Plants-based

products are used since ancient times in controlling mosquitoes and other vectors and are known to be effective as they are environment friendly, less costly, easily biodegradable, has less side effects and are easily available [6, 21].

Table 6. Smoke toxicity of the formulated repellent with respect to the knock down rate of mosquitoes.

Sample Name	Concentration of neem oil (%) in coil	Total burning time (min)	No. of mosquitoes killed in 15 minutes	Total mosquitoes killed in 15 minutes	No. of mosquitoes killed (out of 10)	Total mosquitoes killed
Control	0	61	1	6	3	16
	5	64	1		3	
	10	60	2		4	
	15	67	2		6	
Preparation-I	0	45	1	5	3	13
	5	42	1		3	
	10	40	1		3	
	15	36	2		4	
Preparation-II	0	29	2	10	4	20
	5	35	2		5	
	10	31	3		5	
	15	35	3		6	
Preparation-III	0	24	3	14	6	26
	5	28	3		5	
	10	26	4		7	
	15	22	4		8	
Preparation-IV	0	50	2	9	3	20
	5	54	2		5	
	10	48	2		5	
	15	42	3		7	
synthetic coil	--	51	5	5	12	12

Figure 3: Graphical comparison of repellence property between neem oil coils formulated with different binders and also with synthetic coil.

X axis = Sample taken for study

Y axis = Number of mosquitoes killed in 15 minutes

CONCLUSION

A novel natural mosquito repellent coil was successfully developed and characterized that effectively bridges the gap between safety, efficacy and environmental sustainability. In the present investigation it can be concluded that neem plant can be used an efficient alternative against synthetic mosquito repellent. The neem flower coil with neem powder as a binder, impregnated with 15% neem oil have less residual percentage, shows efficient flammability, does not show irritability and is able to repel mosquitoes effectively and thus is considered as an efficient herbal repellent against mosquitoes. The incorporation of neem oil in a carefully designed mosquito repellent coil base resulted in a product that combines traditional knowledge with modern formulation principles. During this study, mosquito repellent activity of all preparations showed that the product was very efficient and safe to use. Statistically, it showed that the formulated product is very good and safe for use. No volunteers complain about allergic consequences. So, it is a safe product. The formulation was ecological, economical and pocket friendly. Further investigations are needed to elucidate the efficacy of the herbal mosquito repellent formulations against a wide range of mosquito species and also to identify active compounds responsible for mosquito repellent activity to utilize them if necessary, in preparing a commercial product to be used as a mosquito repellent.

Conflict Of Interest Statement:

The author declares no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript. None of the author has any financial or personal relationships with the pharmaceutical brands mentioned in this study or with competing products. The research was conducted independently without any commercial or financial support from pharmaceutical companies or related organizations.

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